

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN DISCONTINUOUS
FIBRE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Tensile and fatigue properties of two aluminium alloys, reinforced with short 'Saffil' alumina fibres (volume fraction = 0.2) have been determined at ambient temperatures. The composites were fabricated by the infiltration of a fibre preform using a squeeze casting operation. Tensile stress-strain plots on the two reinforced alloys (99.85% aluminium (LM0) and an Al-Cu-Mg-Ni-Fe (2618A) alloy) show that the fibres bring about an increase in both elastic modulus (>20%) and in the level of matrix work hardening. The tensile and fatigue strengths of the LM0 are increased by the presence of the fibres whilst those of 2618A alloy are impaired. Short cracks are initiated at a multitude of fibre-matrix interfaces during fatigue loading in four point bending, whilst coarser alumina particles ('shot') can crack in the strong 2618A matrix and initiate matrix crack growth. Crack growth rates are increased by the presence of the alumina fibres in the 2618A alloy matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous fibres, whiskers and particles in the volume fraction range 0.1 to 0.3 have been used by several workers [1-3] to reinforce or strengthen aluminium alloys. The main choice of reinforcements have been α -alumina (Saffil) fibres, silicon carbide whiskers and particles. Such materials are relatively low in cost and effective composite fabrication processes have been developed which can produce net shapes or stock products which could become economically viable. The ability to use this type of reinforcement in a strategic manner has also been put to good use in the automotive industry, e.g. in the crown region of aluminium pistons for the diesel engine, the reinforcement of the metal matrix allowed superior elevated temperature wear, stiffness and strength properties to

be developed (4). In aerospace applications the ability to improve stiffness by the introduction of these reinforcements will become of major importance particularly if this can be done without significant loss of strength, toughness and fatigue resistance in the formed components.

A limited amount of work on the effect of $<1\mu\text{m}$ diameter silicon carbide whisker reinforcement on the toughness and fatigue behaviour of aluminium alloys has been carried out. The addition of a whisker volume fraction of 0.2 has been shown to reduce the fracture toughness of 6061 alloy in the T6 condition from 35 to 7 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ [5]. Microcrack initiation and growth under cyclic loading conditions has been observed by Williams and Fine [6] on the polished surfaces of silicon carbide whisker reinforced 2124 alloys. Little information is available on the toughness and fatigue properties of δ -aluminium (Saffil) discontinuous fibre reinforced aluminium alloys. Some initial work to obtain S-N data under zero-tension loading conditions demonstrated that the introduction of these fibres did not benefit the high stress low cycle fatigue properties of an Al-Si-Mg casting alloy (LM25). But the fibres gave some improvement under these test conditions in a 99.85% pure aluminium matrix (7,8).

This paper describes work on two δ -alumina fibre reinforced aluminium alloys, 2618A and 99.8% pure aluminium (LMO). The 2618A alloy is based on the Al-Cu-Mg system and contains additions of iron, nickel and silicon, it is used for elevated temperature service. It can be precipitation hardened by the $S(\text{Al}_2\text{CuMg})$ phase and has a greater tensile strength than impure aluminium. The effect of δ -alumina fibres on the fatigue properties of these two different matrices has been assessed by determining S-N plots under zero-tension conditions and by observing surface fatigue-crack initiation and growth patterns under four point bending conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The properties of 'Saffil' alumina (RF) grade fibres used as a discontinuous reinforcement are shown in Table 1. The composition of the two matrix alloys are given in Table 2; the aluminium matrix (LMO) was in the as-cast condition whilst the 2618A alloy matrix had been solution

treated at 520°C, cold water quenched and then aged at 190°C for 16h (T6 treatment).

TABLE 1
Properties of 'Saffil' alumina fibres (RF grade)

Composition	96-97% Al ₂ O ₃	Crystal phase	α-alumina
Mean diameter	3μm	Elastic modulus	300 GPa
Breaking strength	2000 MPa	Breaking strain	0.67%

TABLE 2
Chemical composition of aluminium alloys

	%Cu	%Mg	%Si	%Fe	%Mn	%Ti	%Ni	%Al
LM0	-	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	-	-	99.85
2618A (RR58)	2.0	1.23	0.20	1.23	0.15	0.13	0.92	Rem.

Composite fabrication

To produce both the unreinforced and reinforced materials a process of "squeeze forming" was adopted. Fibre preforms (or pads) of 0.6 g/cm³ density were preheated to 600°C and inserted in to a heat die (220°C) prior to injection of the superheated metal (≈750°C). The die set produced a cylindrical part which contained a disc shaped fibre reinforced region (110mm diameter and 11mm thick). At a constant speed of 20mm/s the punch was introduced into the die and a maximum pressure of 80MPa was applied to the metal for a period of ≈2 minutes. The pressure was released and the part stripped in a period of 15 seconds.

Tensile tests

Flat tensile test samples were cut and shaped in at least two directions in each of the discs. The samples had a gauge length of 25mm and a section of 5mm x 5mm. A pair of strain gauges were mounted on the gauge length of each sample and load-deflection plots were recorded using a conventional tensile testing machine.

Fatigue tests

Two forms of fatigue testing were carried out on the unreinforced and reinforced materials:

- a) Tension-tension testing to failure in order to provide data for S-N plots.

- b) Four point bend tests with observations being made on a polished surface of the initiation and propagation of surface cracks.

Tension-tension tests were carried out on similar test pieces (ground to a 1200 grit finish) to those described for the tensile work. A Mayes servohydraulic machine was used for the tests operating under load control at a frequency of 10Hz and an R-ratio of 0.1.

Four point bend tests employed 10 x 10 cross-section x 70mm long bars which had been ground and polished (to a 1 μ m diamond finish) and then etched in a 25% nitric acid-0.5% hydrofluoric acid etch. The four point rig had upper and lower rollers 50mm and 10mm apart respectively. A frequency of 30Hz and an R-ratio of 0.1 were employed on the Mayes servohydraulic machine. Samples were load cycled e.g. 5,000 cycles and then held under a mean load (so that any surface crack was held open). An acetate sheet presoaked in acetone was layed upon the polished upper surface between the upper rollers. After drying the sheet was peeled off and glued to a thin glass slide. Repeated replication of the same surface in this manner after a given number of cycles allowed crack initiation and propagation to be monitored. To assist in the observation of the cracks a gold-palladium coating was vacuum sputtered on to the replica surface. Observations on the replicas were made by optical and electron microscopy.

RESULTS

Tensile behaviour at 20°C

Load-extension plots were analysed carefully from each unreinforced and reinforced material tested. At low strains all material showed elastic behaviour, and in the case of the reinforced materials a significant increase in elastic modulus (>22%) above the relevant matrix material was measured, see Table 3a. Differences were noted in the limits of proportionality of the two matrix materials, i.e. 15MPa (0.02% strain) for the LMO and 280 (0.36% strain) for 2618A. These were then modified by the inclusion of the 'Saffil' reinforcement, in the LMO the stress increased marginally to 21MPa (0.025% strain) whilst for the reinforced 2618A alloy the stress reduced drastically to 87MPa (0.085% strain).

TABLE 3a
Modulus and breaking strengths of matrix and composite materials

Composite/ Alloy	Matrix Condition	Youngs Modulus GPa	Breaking Stress MPa	Breaking Strain %
LM0	As cast	68	40	37
LM0 + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	As cast	83	142	1.1
2618A	T6	77	431	2.5
2618A + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	T6	102	383	0.8

TABLE 3b
Proof stress of matrix and composite materials

Composite/ Alloy	Limit of Proportionality MPa	0.1% Proof Stress MPa	0.2% Proof Stress MPa	0.5% Proof Stress MPa
LM0	15	27	28	29
LM0 + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	21	57	75	116
2618A	280	371	388	416
2618A + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	87	265	317	-

Proof stress measurements were determined at 0.1, 0.2 and 0.5% offset strain. As Table 3b demonstrates, these measurements reveal significant changes in deformation behaviour beyond the limit of proportionality between the reinforced and unreinforced samples. Between the limit and 0.1% offset strain, a stress increase of three times was recorded in the reinforced LM0 and twice in the reinforced 2618A above the values measured on the unreinforced samples. These increases are sustained and even enhanced as the offset strain rises to 0.2% and then to 0.5%. The interaction of the initial elastic behaviour and what appears to be work hardening behaviour does produce differences in the stress-strain plots for the two systems. In the case of the LM0 matrix with a low strain elastic limit the work hardening promoted by the reinforcement dominates, whilst the reduction in strain at the elastic limit of the 2618A

apparently promoted by the reinforcement is also influential. Overall the LM0 appears to be strengthened by the reinforcement and 2618A alloy does not show any improvement over its unreinforced matrix at any offset strain level or in breaking stress, see Table 3b.

The introduction of the reinforcement in both matrix alloys reduces the elongation at failure. In the potentially stronger 2618A matrix the reinforcement reduces the strain to failure (0.8%) close to that which is associated with Saffil fibre strain (0.67%), see Table 3a.

Fatigue life

Plots of stress amplitude versus number of cycles to failure for the two matrix alloys with and without reinforcement are shown in fig. 1. The effect of adding fibres to the low strength LM0 matrix is to increase the fatigue stress significantly at the low cycle high stress end of the

Fig. 1. S-N plot for matrix and composite materials produced under tension-tension loading.

plot through to the high cycle lower stress region. Fatigue stress at 10^6 cycles has been raised three times, i.e. from 25MPa to 77MPa, by adding $V_f = 0.2$ 'Saffil' fibres. In the case of the higher strength matrix 2618A the fibre addition has reduced the fatigue strength under

low and high cycle conditions. At 10^6 cycles the fatigue stress was reduced from 195MPa to 176MPa by $V_f = 0.2$ 'Saffil' fibres. These fatigue strengths represent $\approx 45\%$ of the tensile breaking strengths of the reinforced and unreinforced materials.

The fracture faces of the high cycle fatigue samples produced on the reinforced LMO material show many of the features found on those samples which have been subjected to monotonic tensile failure. A tendency was noted for the height of the ductile metal cusps to be reduced in the case of the fatigue load failures. Fibre debonding and pull out was found with the reinforced LMO samples. Less evidence of matrix ductility and fibre pull out was found on the tensile and fatigue samples of the reinforced 2618A alloy.

Initiation and growth of short fatigue cracks in bending

Examination in the SEM of the replicated polished surfaces of a four point bend sample of the reinforced LMO material showed little evidence of crack initiation at a stress amplitude $\Delta\sigma = 80\text{MPa}$, until the sample had undergone 10^3 cycles. Thereafter a multitude of short cracks began to form mostly at fibre-matrix interfaces which propagated short distances in to the matrix, see fig. 2a. Such cracks after 4×10^3 cycles were between 10 and $30\mu\text{m}$ long. Increasing the number of cycles to 2.5×10^4 cycles has caused many of the cracks to coalesce and to propagate apparently through the fibres, see fig. 2b. Some of the fibre cracks could have been present prior to testing in which case they have opened up by the cyclic loading. Increasing the stress amplitude ($\Delta\sigma$) to 100MPa promotes crack initiation at a reduced number of cycles ($<10^3$), see fig. 2c. Again a number of cracks have formed at fibre-matrix interfaces and here they are 5 to $20\mu\text{m}$ long. As the number of cycles increased further the cracks began to link together.

A different pattern of crack propagation was observed in the case of reinforced 2618A alloy. Higher stress amplitudes were applied, i.e. $\Delta\sigma > 200\text{MPa}$, to this stronger material. After 5×10^3 little evidence was found of cracks even at fibre-matrix interfaces, see fig. 3a. Increasing the number of cycles to 1.5×10^4 does produce a crack in a ceramic particle which is approximately $25\mu\text{m}$ in diameter, see fig. 3b. The crack has propagated completely across the particle and has entered the matrix for a distance of $2-3\mu\text{m}$ at each end. Further replicas of the surface charted the progress of the crack every 5×10^3 cycles. Fig. 3c shows

Fig. 2. Replicated fatigue crack growth produced on the surface of a 4 point bend sample of LMO reinforced with 0.2V_f Al₂O₃: (a) 4 × 10³ cycles at Δσ = 80MPa, (b) 2.5 × 10⁴ cycles at Δσ = 80MPa and (c) 10³ cycles at Δσ = 100MPa.

how the crack has propagated across the matrix and through other ceramic materials including fibres (3μm diameter). The crack appears to have bifurcated in places either where it is emerging from the ceramic to the matrix or in mid-matrix. In the latter case this may not be a bifurcation but the approach of two cracks which have initiated in nearby ceramic particles. Further test samples were observed, e.g. at Δσ = 216MPa, and once again a few cracks were initiated at larger pieces of ceramic and propagation continued in a similar pattern to that already described, see fig. 3d.

Fig. 3. Replicated fatigue crack growth produced on the surface of a 4-point bend sample of 2618A alloy reinforced with $0.2V_f \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$: (a) 5×10^3 cycles at $\Delta\sigma = 200\text{MPa}$, (b) 1.5×10^4 cycles at $\Delta\sigma = 200\text{MPa}$, (c) 4.2×10^5 cycles at $\Delta\sigma = 200\text{MPa}$ and (d) 1.65×10^5 cycles at $\Delta\sigma = 216\text{MPa}$.

From the replicas a plot of crack length (a) vs. number of cycles (N) was obtained for each reinforced 2618A sample. The stress intensities K_{\max} and K_{\min} were calculated from the stress amplitude, mean stress, crack length and compliance data for the test geometry. From these plots and calculated values the crack growth rate (da/dN) was plotted against $K_{\max} - K_{\min} = \Delta K$ for the conditions where the cracks were still relatively short. Fig. 4 demonstrates a number of abrupt variations in crack growth rate, i.e. over two orders of magnitude. Close examination of the replicas in conjunction with the type of plot given in fig. 4 revealed that the varying growth rates were the result of fast crack propagation across ceramic particles or fibres, and slow growth under conditions where cracks emerged from ceramic into the metal matrix. As the cracks grew longer and faster and ΔK increased, the effective size of excursions decreased.

Fig. 4. Crack growth rate (da/dN) versus ΔK plot for short cracks in 2618A alloy reinforced with 0.2V_f Al₂O₃ fibres.

Crack propagation rates in bending

Measurements of crack length were continued on the reinforced 2618A material on the replicated longer cracks and this provided information for a more conventional da/dN versus ΔK plot, see fig. 5. In addition the squeeze cast 2618A material without reinforcement was subject to a similar pattern of testing and a comparative plot was obtained. The data obtained reveals that the presence of the 'Saffil' reinforcement does reduce the ΔK values for the 2618A alloy near threshold and at higher ΔK where one approaches conditions for unstable crack growth.

DISCUSSION

Tensile behaviour

The tensile data on both matrices (IM0 and 2618) demonstrates that the elastic modulus is increased by at least 20% by the addition of the reinforcing 'Saffil' fibres. It would appear that the reinforcement does not bring about a large increase in the limit of proportionality values,

in fact in the case of the 2618 alloy a major reduction has been measured (see Table 3b).

Fig. 5. Crack growth rates (da/dN) versus ΔK plot for long cracks in 2618A alloy reinforced with 0.2V_f Al₂O₃ fibres.

Possible reasons for this reduction could be:

- (a) general or local plastic deformation,
- (b) fibre-matrix debonding,
- (c) residual stresses,
- (d) fibre cracking.

On the basis of observations made on the fatigue samples which have been stressed at higher levels than the limit of proportionality there is little evidence to suggest that (b) and (d) are responsible. Local plastic deformation may take place in areas where fibre volume fraction is low or at fibre ends. Residual stresses can arise because alumina has a smaller coefficient of expansion than aluminium which may leave the matrix in tension after fabrication or heat treatment.

Beyond the limit of proportionality the stress still rises quickly but obviously not as abruptly as if the material was behaving in a completely elastic manner. This would suggest that the distribution of alumina fibres is causing both matrices to work harden at least up to 0.5% offset strain (see Table 3b). Such hardening will result from the interaction of dislocations with the alumina fibres in both matrices and in the case of 2618A alloy the fine distribution of S phase and other

precipitates will also impede dislocation motion.

On the basis of the examination of the fracture surface, failure occurs under monotonic tensile loading conditions due to a combination of

- (a) fibre-matrix debonding,
- (b) the initiation of ductile failure by fibre-matrix debonding,
- (c) fibre fracture.

In the LMO matrix there is little evidence of fibre fracture as there is evidence of lots of fibre pull-out.

Fatigue behaviour

Fig. 1 shows that the introduction of the fibres into the LMO matrix promote a rather different fatigue response to the case with the 2618A matrix. If the tensile stress-strain data is used to specify the strains in the first fatigue cycle, it is noticeable that much higher strains occur in the unreinforced and reinforced LMO than with the 2618A matrix. This is particularly true for failures which occur within 2×10^3 cycles, see Table 4. These strains are above those associated with the limit of

TABLE 4
Fatigue stresses and strains

Material	No. of cycles	Failure stress MPa	*Calculated Fatigue strain %
LMO	2×10^3	35	>0.75
	3×10^6	25	0.37
LMO + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	2×10^3	100	0.53
	3×10^6	70	0.26
2618A	2×10^3	275	0.36
	3×10^6	180	0.25
2618A + 0.2V _f Al ₂ O ₃	2×10^3	230	0.31
	3×10^6	160	0.20

*Maximum % strain in the first fatigue cycle calculated from tensile stress-strain plots.

proportionality. In the case of the unreinforced 2618A matrix the initial fatigue strain does not exceed that at the tensile limit of proportionality. The reinforced 2618A alloy does exceed this strain at 2×10^3 and 3×10^6 cycles. It would appear that the alumina fibres are

able to reduce the plastic strain of LM0 whilst causing the 2618A matrix to experience greater levels of plastic strain.

Short crack initiation

In the LM0 matrix it has been demonstrated that cracks can initiate at fibre-matrix interfaces at $\Delta\sigma$ values $\gg 80$ MPa and after 10^3 stress cycles. According to the tensile related data such stresses could produce large initial strains in excess of 0.4%. Under these conditions the large amount of matrix deformation may promote interface debonding particularly if the bond is relatively weak.

The potentially stronger 2618A matrix probable does not see such large strains (initially less than 0.3% at $\Delta\sigma = 200$ MPa). No evidence of fibre-matrix debonding was found under these conditions after $>10^3$ cycles. Eventually cracking does occur at large ceramic particles. This could be assisted by local stress concentrations which could develop in a heavily work hardened matrix. The particles are rather larger than the fibres and arise in the alumina fibre production process and are called 'shot'. Once a $25\mu\text{m}$ long crack has been produced in this way it appears to propagate at varying rates depending upon whether it is passing through metal or ceramic. The slow stages appear to occur at the point of emergence from the ceramic into the metal. The observed behaviour does relate to the kind of observations made on short crack behaviour in conventional alloys where cracks initiate at second phase particles and then interact with grain boundaries and other particles as they propagate [9].

Crack propagation

Two mechanisms appear to operate, in the case of the more ductile matrix (LM0) there are many short interface cracks. Propagation occurs by the linking of these short cracks. This type of behaviour appears to relate to the kind of observations which have been made by Williams and Fine [4] on samples of silicon carbide whisker reinforced 2124 alloys.

The crack growth behaviour in the reinforced 2618A matrix involves a small number of short cracks which eventually propagate according to the Paris crack growth equation. However, the introduction of the alumina fibres does not appear to improve the crack growth resistance of 2618A alloys. The growth of long cracks is not impeded by the fibres and the growth rate is increased at high, intermediate and threshold ΔK levels, see fig. 5.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The introduction of 'Saffil' alumina fibres ($V_f = 0.2$) in an aluminium matrix can produce an improvement in elastic modulus.
- (2) The fibres will not necessarily improve the stress level at which matrix plastic deformation begins. In certain cases (2618A alloy in the T6 condition) this stress is significantly reduced by their introduction.
- (3) Lower strength (LM0) and higher strength matrices (2618A) work harden considerably when a fibre volume fraction of 0.2 is present.
- (4) The fatigue properties follow the tensile behaviour, i.e. the addition of alumina increases the monotonic and fatigue strength of LM0 and reduces the same two properties of 2618A alloy.
- (5) Short cracks will initiate and grow in both the reinforced LM0 and 2618A alloys. In the case of LM0 it is by matrix fibre debonding at high strain levels and in 2618A cracks occur in some larger ($25\mu\text{m}$) ceramic particles which have formed during fibre production.
- (6) In the reinforced LM0 matrix the short cracks appear to coalesce to form a continuous crack which propagates around fibres and through matrix.
- (7) Propagation of long cracks in the stronger 2618A alloy matrix took place through fibres and matrix. The crack growth rate of 2618A was increased at high, intermediate and near threshold ΔK values by the presence of the alumina fibres.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are indebted to Dr. J. Johnson and Mr. R. Jones of Rolls-Royce Ltd., Derby; Dr. J. Dinwoodie of ICI plc, Mond Division, Runcorn; and Mr. J. Barlow of GKN Technology Ltd., Wolverhampton, for the provision of materials and general support. They also wish to acknowledge the provision of a studentship (TEW) by the Science and Engineering Research Council.

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